

RESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: LIONETTI

FIRST NAME: MICHELE

PROGRAM CODE: DIDOL

COURSE CODE: A401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 1

INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)The author used the following software: LibreOffice (document converted to docx)

THE ART OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

As the academic writing is essential to complete a doctoral program, the course ACA-401D is a detailed and extensive path to learn, and improve this art. I need to understand the rules of a good academic writing to achieve success at the university and to begin to engage in academic dialogue. In the following, I will describe the content of the *Period 1 Coursepack*.

2) STRUCTURING AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

“An academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence” (EUCLID 2019, 2). The idea has to be based on evidence and examples. It is an answer to a question. The essay begins with a thesis (the idea or the answer to a question) that have to be developed by reasoning and giving evidence, by the logical connection of points, by the construction of a logical path that justify it. It needs to construct an initial plan of the essay, working out the initial thoughts. This initial plan helps guide the research: it suggests how the question can be answered, which information to use, it gives an initial structure to the essay that can be changed in the proceeding process of writing activity.

The parallel *Researching Phase* consists in the selection of readings relevant for the essay. This phase can change the original plan of the essay because the readings are a source of new suggestions and ideas. Academic writing draws on the work of other writers and researchers. Reading and researching are vital to essay writing. Researching activity provides the knowledge and evidence. It allows you to develop a thesis and argument to answer the essay question (EUCLID 2019, 3).

The organization of ideas in a structure and in a draft is a process that have to be revised many times before to reach the definitive form. However, it is important to stay focused and to avoid that the referencing activity does not distract the writer from the thesis.

The essay structure can be divided ideally in four main parts: the introduction, the body, the conclusion, the references. The references, in last part of the research, are a list of sources cited in the text and used to give evidence, to support the thesis, to develop the discussion. The introduction declares the thesis. The body develop the discussion to support the thesis by a logical path and giving examples and evidences. “When you attribute views to the person whose ideas you are addressing, indicate the evidence for the attribution by noting relevant passages” (EUCLID 2019, 44). Citations give emphasis to main concepts, underline them, give examples and support the thesis. The conclusion resumes the paper and show the thesis as a result of a logical path.

3) **THE FORM OF AN ACADEMIC ESSAY**

It is important the form in which a research is presented. The format of the text needs to be standardized. In such a way the readers can found a common frame in which the main information can be localized in the dedicated sections. Euclid University provides templates, that permit to adopt a standard for the different tasks of the programs. At the same time, the file name standardization permit to associate the file with a particular program and course.

As two main version of English exists (US or UK), It needs to choose one of them at beginning because there are differences, in the punctuation and in the grammar and in other minor issues that give to a paper a consistent aspect.

4) **PLAGIARISM**

One of the most important things is avoid plagiarism. Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit (EUCLID 2019, 9).

Quoting, paraphrasing, copying and pasting is possible only if writer gives credit to the original author. Plagiarism is not fair, unethical and a serious academic offense. Always the ethical writer cites the author or source that has provided the information. In such a way the research activity is presented as a progressive process where different opinions can get a common knowledge in a topic. Plagiarism can be avoided declaring the sources with in-text direct or paraphrasing citations and with a *References* section. The sources are the readings selected in the *Researching phase* described above. “In order to avoid plagiarism the solution is to properly CITE the author or source that has provided the information you are using” (EUCLID 2019, 13).

5) **CITATIONS**

There are two aspects to consider: *in-text citation* and *list of works cited*. *In-text citation* refers to citing the piece of work the writer is using within the text itself. After the citation, it needs to put the authors name in parenthesis with the page number that the information came from. When the writer quotes the exact words of an author, he must use quotation marks “” to capture the words. This is called quotation. When a quotation is a long one it will take no quotation marks but will be indented and look like a separate little paragraph.

Another way to cite is with a paraphrase. Paraphrasing is the activity to cite the ideas and information from a source but written in your own words (EUCLID 2019, 23). Always, it follows the authors name in parenthesis with the page number that the information came from.

Alternatively, it can be used a signal phrase, (e.g., “point out”). In this case the writer has to use the author’s name in the beginning with the signal phrase and put after the citation only the page number in parenthesis. This example can show how to use a signal phrase: Adam Smith in *The Theory of Moral Sentiments* points out that “...” (143).

In the *References*, the publication information for the sources have different formatting rules for different kind of sources (e.g., books, websites, videos). EUCLID *Period 1 Coursepack* gives some examples regarding how to reference different kind of sources. When in-text citations do not use the parenthesis with the author name and page number but use the footnote style, it does not need to add a *References* section at the end of the paper. Word processors give tools to manage footnotes automatically.

6) **THE LOGICAL FLOW**

The logical flow in a paper can be reached with a structure of headings, titles, sections. This is a way to organize the ideas presented. Additionally, the use of logical connectors is important (“However,” “Nevertheless,” “On the one hand,” “On the other hand,” “In spite of this,” “For this reason,” “As a result,” “Moreover,” “Furthermore,” etc.) (EUCLID 2019, 40). The correct use of the comma, of the punctuation, of the numerals vs the cardinals and of other grammar issues, helps to write clearly and improves the logical flow of a paper.

EUCLID gives a list of *Latin Abbreviations and Expressions* to use in a paper. They permit to express clearly some concepts and features and help to reach the logical flow too.

7) **STYLES**

All what discussed above constitutes a style. “A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent” (EUCLID 2019, 52). EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian) as writing style and provides templates for the different tasks that are based on that style. In a style it would be contained accepted terminology, the use of symbols, the use of active form vs passive forms, the use of the US vs UK English, the way to do citations, etc. You

can see a style as a collection of rules and ways to write, to organize, to format the content. Different styles can satisfy different work environment or discipline environments. For example, economists and physicists can prefer different styles.

8) **CONCLUSION**

I have previous experience in academic writing, for different audiences in education and physics. This course gives me the opportunity to explore deeply the reasons that guide the adoption of a style for an essay writing. As I am not a native English the considerations regarding the use of the punctuation and the grammar are really useful to improve my competencies. This course will refresh and improve my competencies in essay. I appreciate the *EUCLID ACA-401D -Period 1 Coursepack*. It is detailed and clear and solved some of my doubts regarding citations and plagiarism.

REFERENCES

Euclid University. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1. Washington DC: Euclid University Press*

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.